

RAINDROP: A Framework for Real-Time Holistic Underwater Acoustic Maps

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Abstract: *RAINDROP is a framework for real-time holistic underwater acoustic maps, targeting applications in acoustic Digital Twins of the Ocean (DTOs). It takes a top-to-bottom approach, starting with input collection and preparation, followed by simulation setup and execution, and finally post-processing and visualization of results. Its framework nature offers a structure that users can use to couple the latest developments at each step of the solution process. All in a performance-oriented approach that includes embedded parallelization to achieve faster than real-time calculations. In the present work, the latest release of RAINDROP is presented and the coupling/automatization of one of its solvers, KRAKEN, based on normal modes theory, is successfully verified against the 3D penetrable wedge benchmark. Then, RAINDROP is applied in a practical scenario, to assess the impact of shipping noise during the military NATO exercise REPMUS2024 in Tróia and Sesimbra, in Portugal. The environmental inputs are collected from EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Data Store. AIS data from shipping is farmed from aisstream.io and the equivalent acoustic source of each vessel is modeled using the JOMOPANS-ECHO model. A total of 38 days are simulated, focusing on the 63 Hz frequency, achieving calculations up to 25 times faster than real-time. The results are post-processed using the concept of Level of Onset of Biological Effects (LOBE) by the TG Noise under EU's Marine Strategy Framework Directive, demonstrating the potential and capabilities of RAINDROP.*

Keywords: *RAINDROP, Computational Ocean Acoustics, Verification, 3D Wedge, REPMUS2024*

1. INTRODUCTION

Computational ocean acoustics has been the subject of research and development for many decades already. A popular suite of tools concerns the open-source Acoustics Toolbox, distributed under the Ocean Acoustics Library¹ (OALib). It offers a FORTRAN implementation of several acoustic propagation solvers, such as KRAKEN [1] (normal modes theory) and BELLHOP [2] (ray theory). As part of a community effort, the toolbox has advanced significantly

¹<https://oalib-acoustics.org>

since its inception, including with the addition of MATLAB and Python interfaces. Moreover, new flavors and variations of the solvers have also evolved.

Despite all of this progress, it can be argued that these tools remain dispersed and lack standardization. This leads to steep learning curves that hinder the correct usage of the solvers by less experienced users and limits the complexity of the cases one can develop. Indeed, computational ocean acoustics for practical scenarios is a complex problem, that involves several environmental inputs and approximations that can have a profound impact on the solution and its accuracy.

This consideration is becoming increasingly important as stakeholders from academia, industry and public sector are required to use computational ocean acoustics as part of the solutions to monitor and mitigate excess levels of underwater noise. For example, the European Union's Marine Strategy Framework Directive [3], under Descriptor 11, directs its Member States to keep track and periodically report on this topic following the recommendations of the respective Technical Group (TG). Moreover, the dimension of underwater noise pollution also permeates shipping [4] and other offshore activities, and computational acoustics is becoming indispensable for environmental impact assessment and design of strategies to reduce it. Also, it can be useful to numerically assess how sound propagates underwater, which is important for certain communication and sonar applications, in order to maximize their performance.

Seminal works, such as the EU project JOMOPANS [5], set already some of the foundations for more complex applications of computational ocean acoustics - in this case to model shipping noise. Moreover, in the market, some tools already exist that substantiate this more elaborate and practical side of computational ocean acoustics, such as dbSEA [6] and Qonops [7]. However, these are commercial, closed-source alternatives. While having their own intrinsic value, we feel that the community could greatly benefit from an open-source alternative. Particularly one that facilitates the integration and dissemination of new developments, supports their application to practical scenarios, and promotes the replication of results.

Besides, with the inception of Hydrotwin² in 2023, a state-of-the-art acoustic Digital Twin of the Ocean [8], there was a need for software to create the virtual representation of underwater acoustic environments. To our best knowledge, there was no tool that was oriented to such emerging application, which implies a high-level of automation and efficiency. Due to all of these reasons, RAINDROP³ started its development at around the same time. While still in late stages of development, with a small set of beta testers, it is intended to be eventually made open-source to the community.

2. RAINDROP

RAINDROP is a holistic framework for computational ocean acoustics, oriented for emerging Digital Twins of the Ocean (DTOs) applications, where automatization and efficiency of the virtual models are key. RAINDROP is structured in four major areas that we have identified as critical for its success, which are presented in Figure 1.

The first is related to input data collection and preparation – at the moment, RAINDROP is capable of automatically connecting and processing relevant data from popular open-source databases from the European Union, such as EMODnet⁴ (bathymetry) and Copernicus Marine

²<https://hydrotwin.ai>

³<https://github.com/blueOceanSustainableSolutions/RAINDROP>

⁴<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>

Figure 1: RAINDROP overview.

Data Store⁵ (water temperature and salinity profiles).

The second area is the characterization of acoustic sources, either via pre-defined models or user-provided. RAINDROP already has some embedded models, such as JOMOPANS-ECHO [9] for shipping, and is at the moment finalizing the implementation of in-house models for offshore wind turbines. Nevertheless, the user is also capable of providing its own models/data, either calculated by other numerical tools (e.g. CFD, FEM) or experiments.

The third and most critical area focuses on automating the setup and execution of complex simulations, which starts with the simplification of inputs via a single standard YAML file. RAINDROP is also solver-agnostic, with the goal of offering multiple flavors of acoustic models to take advantage of their unique strengths, and even make them work in tandem. Right now, RAINDROP has integrated (and automated) some of the main open-source solvers of OALib, including KRAKEN, the solver used in this paper - note that the direct usage of these solvers requires a lot of manual set-up for complex cases. There is also on-going work on parallelization, with a successful implementation already available and tested in High-Performance Computing (HPC) platforms.

Finally, RAINDROP also provides modules to systematize and post-process the results, based on best-practices available. One example are the TG Noise recommendations for both continuous [10] and impulsive [11] noise. Some routines are already implemented and can be used in the reporting of underwater noise levels by stakeholders. The results are produced in popular data-exchange formats, such as NetCDF, to facilitate dissemination.

3. WEDGE ANALYTICAL CASE

As part of the on-going Verification&Validation (V&V) of RAINDROP, we recover a popular case in the literature with analytical solution, the 3D penetrable wedge. We adopt the analytical solution obtained in [12], based on the adiabatic mode parabolic equations - valid for small apex angles. It is compared with the numerical simulation by RAINDROP using KRAKEN3D as the solver. A schematic of the 3D wedge and its characteristics are presented in Figure 2 and Table 1, respectively.

The wedge's bathymetry is constructed in RAINDROP as a regular 100 by 100 point grid, in which the normal modes are solved. The maximum phase speed, c_{max} , is set to 2500 m/s, and the vertical discretization set to automatic in KRAKEN3D. In order to obtain the complex pressure field based on the normal modes, RAINDROP also executes FIELD3D on the elements of a Delaunay triangulation of the former grid. One of the options is compared: a standard (STD) run of FIELD3D, based on a series of 2D simulations over the bearing direction; or a gaussian beam tracing (GBT) one, which as the name indicates additionally relies on a series of rays emitted to incorporate horizontal refraction effects, thus better capturing the 3D nature of the

⁵<https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products>

solution. A comparison of the analytical solution against RAINDROP is presented in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 2: Schematic of 3D wedge case.

Table 1: Variables of 3D wedge case.

	Description	Value
f	Source Frequency	50 Hz
z_s	Source Depth	10 m
α	Bottom Slope	5 deg
h_0	Bottom Depth	90 m
c_w	Speed Sound Water	1500 m/s
c_b	Speed Sound Bottom	2000 m/s
ρ_w	Density Water	1 g/cm ³
ρ_b	Density Bottom	2 g/cm ³
α_b	Attenuation Bottom	0.5 dB/ λ

Figure 3: Transmission loss over XZ plane @ $z = 10$ m.

Figure 4: Transmission loss over XY plane @ $z = 10$ m.

It is evident that the STD run fails to capture some of the 3D effects present in this benchmark case. On the other hand, the selection of GBT significantly improves this, and the agreement of both solutions is quite satisfactory. Still, the numerical solution of RAINDROP starts to slowly deviate due to small phase differences that build up. This effect has also been observed by the authors in [13] when applying KRAKEN3D directly to this same 3D wedge case. Thus, with this small exercise, one can verify that the coupling and automation of KRAKEN3D within RAINDROP is correctly implemented.

4. REPMUS2024

The Robotic Experimentation and Prototyping with Maritime Unmanned Systems (REPMUS) is organized annually by the Portuguese Navy, taking place in Tróia and Sesimbra, in

Portugal. It counts with the participation of several NATO countries, and involves a significant number of maritime operations. In the 2024 edition blueOASIS participated for the second time with RAINDROP, which can be used not only to assess the environmental impact of the exercise, but also to estimate how sound propagates and its levels, which is essential for operations that require underwater acoustics for communications or localization - all in real-time.

The exercise had a duration of 19 days, between 09/09/2024 and 27/09/2024. The baseline scenario used to assess the impact consists on the 19 days immediately before, from 19/08/2024 to 06/09/2024. RAINDROP was the tool used to prepare the inputs, execute the simulation and post-process the results. A model of the region was created using bathymetry information from EMODnet: DTM F3 Tile [14] (resolution of $1/16^{th}$ arc-minutes) and some other high-resolution data products available along the coastline (resolution of $1/128^{th}$ arc-minutes) and estuary (resolution of $1/64^{th}$ arc-minutes) by Instituto Hidrográfico. The domain spans from 9.30° W to 8.70° W in the longitude direction (~ 53 km) and 38.00° N to 38.55° N in the latitude direction (~ 62 km). The final bathymetry can be visualized in Figure 5, whereas in Figure 6 the respective Delaunay triangulation, including the refinement zone in the Sado estuary mouth, can be visualized.

Figure 5: Input bathymetry.

Figure 6: Delaunay triangulation.

While the Sound Speed Profile (SSP) is known to have a considerable impact on how sound propagates, in the present work it is assumed to be constant both spatially and temporally - overall, the SSP shape did not change significantly based on a preliminary analysis performed. The daily SSP was extracted from the Atlantic - Iberian Biscay Irish - Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast dataset [15] from the Copernicus Marine Data Store at one of the deepest points of the domain, around (38.288° N, 9.300° W), and averaged over the 38 days under analysis into the SSP in Figure 7.

As for the composition of the seabed, it is quite heterogeneous based on available data by Instituto Hidrográfico under the SEPLAT [16] program. Yet, most of the region of interest is of sand type. Therefore, it was assumed an uniform sandy seafloor, based on the properties described in [17].

Another key input is the AIS data, which was farmed from aisstream.io⁶ and stored in a database. It was cleaned *a posteriori* for typical anomalous situations in AIS messages, such as extreme speeds and lengths, or even vessels with nonexistent MMSI which couldn't be objectively characterized. In Figure 8 there is a density map of ship locations via AIS messages

⁶<https://aisstream.io>

before (199 unique vessels) and during (226 unique vessels) REPMUS2024 - it is evident an increase in traffic near Sesimbra during the exercise.

Figure 7: Sound Speed Profile.

Figure 8: AIS density map.

Once again, RAINDROP used the KRAKEN3D solver, based on the theory of normal modes, to solve the underwater acoustic propagation. Some of the relevant settings are presented in Table 2. For increased performance, FIELD3D was executed with the STD option. Based on the previous 3D wedge case, we know that this option led to some phase differences in relation to the analytical solution. However, the average Transmission Loss values were not significantly impacted. Considering that the end-goal of this case is to analyze Sound Pressure Level (SPL) trends over large periods of time, it is assumed that such phase difference will be averaged out, with minimal impact.

All the configuration is done via a YAML file, and only a few commands are required to start RAINDROP, which fully automatizes the simulation setup and execution. First, the normal modes are obtained using KRAKEN3D, assuming that the environmental conditions do not change. Then, FIELD3D is used to obtain the pressure field of each source/vessel for every timestep. This information is aggregated in periods of 5 minutes, to minimize source flickering when AIS messages are sent at a slow rate. The Sound Level of each vessel is characterized using the JOMOPANS-ECHO model [9] and the respective AIS information. Finally, the acoustic pressure field obtained for each individual source is summed and the resulting field transformed to SPL. Note that it was necessary to assume a value for background ambient noise, since only shipping was modeled: 80 dB re $1\mu\text{Pa}$, in line with hydrophone data collected around this region in [18].

An example timeframe of one of the simulations is presented in Figure 9. Note that more than 10000 individual frames were calculated to simulate the period before and during REPMUS2024. Taking advantage of RAINDROP's parallelization, a frame was calculated every 12 seconds using 24-cores in a workstation equipped with an AMD Ryzen Threadripper PRO 3975WX 32-cores @ 4.1 GHz - 25 times faster than real-time.

Leveraging some of the post-processing routines implemented in RAINDROP, some of which inspired by the recommendations of TG Noise for continuous noise [10], the concept of Level of Onset of Biologically Adverse Effects (LOBE) is applied. For this exercise, the domain is subdivided into arbitrary habitats/cells of 2 km by 2 km each. For each its computed the percentage of time in which a certain LOBE threshold was exceeded - arbitrarily set to 90 dB re $1\mu\text{Pa}$ in this case. In Figures 10 and 11, the percentage of time the LOBE was exceeded before

and during REPMUS is presented. The difference between both is presented in Figure 12. It is noticeable an increase of this LOBE exceedance metric between the mouth of the estuary, the coast of Sesimbra and far offshore, in part consistent with the higher density of AIS messages received in some of the areas. On the other end, along Portugal's southern coast until Sines, it is actually observed a reduction in LOBE exceedance. However, all differences are small (<5 %) and even the global value of LOBE exceedance is never above 25%, which can be considered an acceptable value.

On the other hand, these differences can still be under the uncertainty introduced by the simplifications assumed. It is also important to bear in mind that REPMUS involves the operation of many other unmanned vehicles, both surface and underwater, which are not taken into account (no AIS) despite contributing to the soundscape. Also, higher-frequencies may be more critical, both in terms of emissions by the vessels in the area and impact on local populations (e.g. bottlenose dolphins).

All in all, a more in-depth analysis is necessary in order to extract more precise conclusions. This includes the improvement of the temporal/spatial accuracy of some of the inputs, like the SSP and seabed properties. Moreover, modeling other acoustic sources, like wind interaction with the free-surface, is expected to reduce the number of approximations and further increase

Table 2: Variables of REPMUS2024 case.

	Description	Value
f	Source Frequency	63 Hz
z_s	Source Depth	6 m
c_b	Speed Sound Bottom	1650 m/s
ρ_b	Density Bottom	1.9 g/cm ³
α_b	Attenuation Bottom	0.8 dB/ λ
N	Discretization Points	16650
Δt	Timestep	5 min

Figure 9: Example acoustic map.

Figure 10: LOBE exceedance: before REPMUS2024.

Figure 11: LOBE exceedance: during REPMUS2024.

Figure 12: Variation of LOBE exceedance before and during REPMUS2024.

the fidelity of the simulation. Also, a sensitivity and uncertainty analysis could help understand better the relative impact of each component in the final result. This, together with validation against hydrophone data collected during the exercise by blueOASIS, is left as future work.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented RAINDROP, a framework for holistic real-time underwater acoustic maps that targets DTO applications. The coupling and automatization of one of its acoustic solvers, KRAKEN3D, is successfully verified using the popular benchmark case of the 3D penetrable wedge. Then, RAINDROP is applied to a practical case, to assess the environmental impact of REPMUS2024 exercise in the region of Tróia and Sesimbra, in Portugal. The capabilities of RAINDROP to collect and process the input data are demonstrated, and a span of 38 days are simulated, up to 25 times faster than real-time, taking advantage of its parallelization. In the end, a simplified analysis inspired by the metrics set by the TG Noise for continuous noise [10] is presented as proof-of-concept. Assuming a threshold of 90 dB re $1\mu\text{Pa}$, only a slight increase in LOBE exceedance was obtained during the REPMUS2024 exercise, up to 5% more. Still, globally this threshold is never exceeded more than 25% of the time, so the impact can be considered minimal in the 63 Hz frequency band.

As future work, it is planned a more in-depth V&V study of RAINDROP, with sensitivity analysis and uncertainty quantification, taking into consideration more detailed environmental inputs and effects. Data collected by Hydrotwin's network of smart acoustic recorders in Azores will be leveraged to support this effort. During this time, RAINDROP will continue its development, targeting its open-source release.

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